

ISic3559

I.Sicily inscription 3559

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Drepanum

Place of origin (modern)

Trapani

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost, Museo Pepoli (Trapani) ms. 33 and 221

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI337223

1. [— — — — (?) — — — —]
2. πάση ἀρετῇ [—] σοφία [—] καὶ ΤΗ ΠΙΤΑΝΗ
3. Κλαυδίου [— —] Γα[ί]ου
4. ἐποίησε καὶ ἐνεωτέ [ρισε]
5. μνήμης χάριν.
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645634

EDCS 71000780

PHI 337223

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 52.0904

Filippi, A. 2002. Trapani: testimonianze storiche ed archeologiche. *Sicilia Archeologica*. 35: 73-87. At 75 no.13/4

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